

Institute *of* **Physics**

**Environmental
Physics Group**

Newsletter

June 2001

Editor's Report

The second Newsletter for 2001 contains reports of the Annual General Meeting on 16 May and on several recent meetings organised or sponsored by the Environmental Physics Group. Several further meetings are in active preparation but the only firm date at present is the half-day meeting at the Institute on Wednesday 31 October. The subject is Environment and Sustainable Agriculture, a topic that has risen sharply in economic, political and social importance in recent months. The meeting will be supported by the Environmental Chemistry Group of the Royal Society of Chemistry, and full details will be circulated to members in a special mailing in due course.

The Newsletter also includes an account of the first decade's work of the EPG Education Committee, culminating in the publication this April of a new textbook targeted at A-level /First-year undergraduate students. A review of this book will be included in a future issue of the Newsletter.

Derek Rose

ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS GROUP

10th ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING

London, 16th May 2001

MINUTES

The assembled members were welcomed to the AGM by the Chairman, Professor Edward Youngs, who proceeded to present his report for the year (see elsewhere in this issue). This was followed by a report given by the Honorary Secretary, which included a financial statement (also see in this issue). Further breakdown of the expenditure through the year 2000 was presented at the AGM.

There were two retirements from the committee to report. Dr Sian Bethan and Dr Barbara Gabrys were thanked for their efforts over the two years that each has served. As the committee was one understrength last year, this meant there were three vacancies on the committee. There were three nominations for ordinary committee members, as follows:

Dr Karen Aplin, University of Hertfordshire
Ms Sheila Morris, University of Bristol
Ms Lucy Parkin, WS Atkins

These three were elected on to the committee unanimously.

The Chairman, Edward Youngs reminded the meeting that next year both he and the Secretary, Peter Hodgson would be stepping down, having come by then to the end of their term as Group officers.

The AGM concluded with a brief discussion. John Stewart raised the question of what might be done with the financial resources currently at the Group's disposal. Peter Hodgson replied that ideas such as funding a programme of visits into schools, an extension to the bursary scheme and an EPG prize have been discussed in recent committee meetings. This led to several comments and ideas, especially in relation to the suggested visit programme.

CHAIRMAN'S REPORT

Last year our Annual General Meeting was held during our well-attended Tenth Anniversary Meeting that had as its theme the Diversity of Environmental Physics. Seven speakers and several posters showed some, but by no means all, the diverse activities of Members. The scope and breadth of our subject area was further illustrated at this meeting by a photographic display produced by Peter Hughes that recorded some of the personalities, activities, locations and instrumentation involved in environmental physics.

The Group organised two meetings during this last year, both concerned with the effect of the physical environment on health. The first was a lecture last June, held jointly with the London and South East Branch, by John Swanson of the National Grid Company who gave a talk entitled "Do electromagnetic fields cause cancer and how can physicists help to find out". The second was the Congress meeting in March, held jointly with the Medical Physics Group, on "The Physical Environment and Health" at which about fifty attended. We sponsored the International Conference on Urban Air Quality, the third one to be held, this time in Greece in March this year. Lastly, some of us enjoyed an interesting visit to the BBC Weather Station in April. Numbers were limited for this visit and many Members who wished to go were disappointed.

Future events start with a talk after this meeting on "Prospects for Renewable Energy" by Professor Dennis Anderson of Imperial College. In October we are having a meeting with the Environmental Chemistry Group of the Royal Society of Chemistry on the "Environment and Sustainable Agriculture". Looking further ahead, the Group intends to organise a meeting at the Applied Optics Divisional Conference in Cardiff in September 2002. We hope also to arrange other meetings, for example on Bioaerosols and on the Built Environment, and visits to places of interest. The Committee welcomes suggestions of topics for meetings and visits from Members.

The Education Sub-committee is now ten years old. Peter Hughes, the chairman of this committee, reports that the introductory textbook on environmental physics entitled "Planet Earth, Climate and Life: an introduction to environmental physics" has now been published. He also reports that A-level options for schools have changed with environmental options being dropped by some examination boards. This requires a reappraisal of the aims of the Sub-Committee, perhaps focussing at a more junior level.

The Committee continues to assist the Institute with submissions on government reports on environmental matters. Douglas Peirson has been particularly involved with these reports. He is involved with the Foresight panels on Energy and Natural Environment and on Built Environment and Transport, and has recently accepted the invitation from the Institute to serve as its representative on the Environmental Group of the Science Council.

Barbara Gabrys has been in charge of the Group's WEB page and we thank her for the work she has done in setting this up. Members should be aware of the electronic Bulletin

Board which is available for their use. Derek Rose continues as Editor of the Newsletter. There have been some unavoidable delays in sending out the Newsletter this year, but the aim is to have three issues per year. Members are invited to contribute news and comments for publication.

Barbara Gabrys and Sian Bethan are resigning from the Committee. We thank them and the other Committee Members, in particular our Secretary Peter Hodgson, for the work they have all done for the Group.

E.G. Youngs

FINANCIAL SUMMARY 2000-2001

2000 Finances

Balance b/fwd	£2,337.55
2000 Budget award	£4,578.00
Adjustment from 1999	£70.00
Expenditure	(£3,664.04)
Balance c/fwd	£3,321.51

2001 Finances

Balance b/fwd	£3,321.51
2001 Budget award	£4,854.00
Expenditure to 20/3/01	(£701.12)
Balance @ 20/3/01	£7,474.39

SECRETARY & TREASURER'S REPORT

Group membership is now at 555, a small increase on last year's figure. Although the Newsletter and other mailings will remain the prime means of informing members about events, I hope to make more use of email to communicate with EPG members, especially for early notification and final reminders of events. Roughly 2/3 of EPG members now give an email address for correspondence - about 10% of these result in returned messages. Please keep your contact details, as held by the IoP, up to date.

The database of member's interests, set up last year, has already proved its worth. We now have information on the interests and expertise of over 100 members. Notices will appear periodically in the Newsletter, to allow new members the opportunity to register their interests and existing members to update their details. Thanks to all who have contributed to this valuable resource.

The EPG travel bursary scheme is operating well. Last year two awards, totalling £140 were made, in connection with the 10th anniversary meeting. This year, three awards have already been made to a value of £315, in connection with the 3rd International Congress on Urban Air Quality and the Physical Environment & Health meeting at the Physics Congress. The aim of the bursary scheme is to play a part in cultivating a lively and active Group and I think it is succeeding in that respect.

A financial summary is given on the adjacent page. Expenditure last year was largely made up of printing & postage, committee expenses and costs associated with the 10th anniversary meeting. The Group is in a healthy financial situation and we are committed to using this to enhance the Environmental Physics Group community, wherever its members may be.

All that remains is for me to thank Edward Youngs and the rest of the committee for all their efforts over the past year.

Peter Hodgson

May 2001

REPORTS OF MEETINGS

BBC Weather Centre Visit

Twelve members of the Environmental Physics Group had the opportunity to visit the BBC Weather Centre at BBC TV Centre, Wood Lane, London on 25 April. Members first visited several studios including those where breakfast TV, and Jack Dee's forthcoming show, are filmed. The News and Current Affairs rooms were also visited. Returning to the Weather Centre, group members were given an insight into weather presenters's hectic schedules and saw Helen Willetts filming a broadcast in the BBC's automated studio. The scale of the centre's operation was surprising – they employ over 20 presenters. David Braine, Broadcast Manager, provided an overview of the centre's activities. The visit provided an interesting and informative insight into the behind-the-scenes activities of the BBC.

Sian Bethan

The Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality and the 5th Saturn Workshop Measurement, Modelling and Management Loutraki, Greece 19-23 March 2001

With the help of a travel bursary from the Environmental Physics Group, I was able to attend the above-mentioned conference, organized by the Institute of Physics and supported by AWMA, IUPPA and EURASAP.

The aim was to bring together researchers, engineers, educators and policy makers as a follow up to the previous two conferences that were a success, to discuss the ways to follow in a relatively new area of research, that is urban air quality.

Currently I am reading an MSc degree at the University of Malta, as an educator, to attend such a conference, this was a breakthrough for me. I also had the opportunity to present my early research findings and this definitely helped me to break the ice, increase my self-confidence, practise oral presentations, exchange ideas with experts and get involved within the community of research.

The attendance was encouraging, especially from young researchers like me. Everyone could feel that there is an important future, to improve our air quality. The exchange of ideas, at all times, the will to work in existing networks and to work in new ones proposed there, were in my opinion the strongest points of this conference.

The first day was dedicated to the 5th Saturn Workshop. In my opinion it was a crystal clear example of how a research network should be set up in order to maximize the efforts done by everyone all over Europe. All contributors evaluated their work done up to now and their future needs.

A brilliant idea was to have parallel sessions going on, with the possibility to attend any presentation, together with posters set up in the areas where coffee breaks were taken. This gave the possibility to everyone to continue discussions in an informal way and get to know each other well away from the conference halls.

It occurred to me that two areas of study were pointed out in this conference to be an important landmark for further research and development, in fact any MSc and PhD students could have easily formulated ideas on what to work. These were personal exposure to air pollution and ultra fine particulate matter.

Another area, where I noticed that a great amount of work was done was model evaluation and model development. Here I got the idea to refine my work further and perform an intermodel comparison that might be more purposeful for the end of model development.

My personal view about this conference couldn't be other of great satisfaction for various reasons. The high quality of the work presented as well as for the smooth running of the event and the possibility to enhance both the professional and social contacts make me look forward to work more to have the possibility to attend more conferences in the near future. My views apart, there was a general consent that this was not going to be the last conference on the matter, and that there is room for much more work to be done.

I would like to acknowledge my grateful thanks to the Environmental Physics Group for the financial support to attend this conference and for the significant benefits this has afforded my MSc.

Noel Aquilina

Descending into Ellinikon it is the startling sand-coloured sprawl of Athens that yanks the eye from the scrubby greenness of the hills. A borrowed Baedeker and the IOP conference handbook smoothed my way to Loutraki, but didn't eliminate some frantic running around to check into the hotel then get to conference registration before it closed (so much for KLM's on-time record). The welcome reception that followed was indeed welcome not only for the great food, but for the opportunity to match faces to names from papers I'd read, like Dr. Sokhi and Dr. ApSimon that my supervisor suggested I meet.

Problems with timekeeping seemed to plague all Tuesday sessions, and at one point parallel talks in the Aphrodite room ended earlier which meant I missed the last one. About half the talks were interesting to me, and I particularly appreciated USM.1.3 on effects of simplification on physical models from Dr. Leiti. Although I found poster USM.P1.7 interesting I didn't get a chance to talk to the author, and it was unclear at which poster sessions the presentors were expected to be available. There was more great food at the second welcome reception that night, but I still had trouble deciding who I wanted to meet.

The Wednesday morning sessions seemed to run closer to schedule. For a change I found the plenary session interesting because of PL.2.3 on understanding field data by Dr. Schatzmann. During the coffee break I was able to talk to Dr. Rafailidis about his wind tunnel work and papers I couldn't find. During the free afternoon I played tourist in Athens, seeing a little of the city (climbed the Acropolis, of course) and had dinner with my Greek flatmate's family.

The Thursday sessions seemed most relevant to my interests, and I found the early afternoon presentations RAQ.3.6 by Dr. Bartzis, RAQ.3.7 by Dr. Chauvet and RAQ.3.8 by Dr. Louka to be most helpful as issues like upwind geometry, resolved building details and thermal effects in street canyons were discussed in the context of wind tunnel and field experiments. I had a chance to talk to Dr. Louka about pitched-roof field measurements, and I caught up with Dr. Colbeck briefly. I made it a point to be available to talk to readers about my poster (RAQ.P2.35 on using the Lattice Boltzmann method in urban canyons), but never seemed to be there when people picked up my handouts. It was encouraging to see Dr. Rao's interest in the LB method. The conference dinner was excellent, and the Greek dance performers inspired the general dancing that was still going on when I left at midnight (I remember thinking they had more fun than any other conference group I'd seen).

Since I had to leave early to catch my flight back to Manchester, I was only able to sit through the first two plenary sessions after taking down my poster. Some talks scheduled for later sounded interesting and I would have stayed on if possible. My considered opinion of the UAQ3 was time well spent in a very nice place, and I look forward to the special issue journal of the research papers presented.

Lorenzo de la Fuente

"Where we stand on renewable energy and climate change". Report of a talk given by Prof. Dennis Anderson on 16 May 2001 at Portland Place, arranged by the Environmental Physics Group and London/South East branch.

Prof. Anderson began his talk by establishing the need to exploit all the available sources of energy. In the developed world, the need for energy is roughly constant and is supplied largely by fossil fuels. However in the developing countries, growth is rapid and so is the associated demand for power. There are also about two billion people currently not commercially supplied with energy, who will require power as their countries become more economically important. The world energy demand is significantly increasing, but it is not known by exactly how much. Projected carbon dioxide emissions therefore vary by an order of magnitude; one of the uncertainties is the use of renewable energy.

Renewable energy is potentially able to supply a significant fraction of the world's energy demands. Prof. Anderson discussed several forms of renewable energy, for example solar-thermal energy, in which the sun's rays are focused by parabolic mirrors onto heat-conducting strips, and used to heat water. This is clearly not appropriate for climates such as the UK's, but in California a 150 MW solar-thermal plant has been successfully running for some years. Unfortunately a less progressive administration has recently hindered the development of further plants or technological improvements. The audience was left feeling that renewable energy technology is sadly under-exploited, with much room for innovation.

Prof. Anderson pointed out the two main problems with renewable energy, firstly storage, and secondly proving that it is cost-efficient compared to fossil fuels. There are numerous ways to store energy from renewable sources in the short-term, for example thermally. Long-term storage is lacking, but it seems that the most promising solution is to use the electrolytic dissociation of hydrogen. Prof. Anderson showed that by broadening the function of the National Grid to harvest and store in this way, electricity from renewables could be cheaper than from fossil fuels. However there is still a need to implement the technology, which looks less promising since the UK is one of the countries investing least in renewable Research and Development. Governmental policies appear to be moving in the right direction with financial incentives to develop renewable fuels, but there is still a great deal to be done before the national network is equipped to supply cheap power from renewable fuel.

Karen Aplin

The First 10 years of the Environmental Physics Group's Education Committee,
1990-2000

The Education Committee of the Environmental Physics Group is now 10 years old! Since its inception at the preliminary meeting of interested parties in the formation of an Environmental Physics Group in May 1990, it has become increasingly committed and involved in advancing the cause of Environmental Physics in schools, colleges and universities in the British Isles.

The membership of this committee has been as diverse as the subject itself, and has included:

Mr. Michael Chapple	Middlesex University and Principal Examiner
Mr. Ray Davies	Manchester Grammar School and Salford University
Dr. Sally East	Atmospheric Physics Laboratory, UCL
Mr. Peter Hughes (Chair)	Westminster Kingsway College, London
Professor Colin Honeybourne	University of the West of England
Dr. Nigel Mason (Consultant)	Physics and Astronomy Department, UCL
Professor Alastair McArthur	University of the South Pacific
Mr. David Monteith	Toot Hill School, Nottinghamshire
Dr. Jane Savage	London University Institute of Education
Dr. Francesca Wheeler	Withington Girls' School, Manchester
Mrs. Catherine Wilson MBE	Institute of Physics

Many of the members are actively involved in their particular area of research or interest.

Since 1992 the Committee has been working with several national "A" level curriculum initiatives including:

York University Science Education Group's "Science in the Environment", GNVQ Advanced (Level 3), Supported Learning in Physics Project (SLIPP) for developed between the Institute of Physics and the Open University and which resulted in "Physics in the Environment", and recently "Advancing Physics" spearheaded by Professor Jon Ogborn.

The Committee has been instrumental in bringing Environmental Physics-related modules on to "A" level curricula. These have included (a) "Physics in the Environment" (Oxford and Cambridge Board) and (b) "Earth and Atmosphere" on to the London "A" level Examination Board and developing the curriculum support materials for their successful dissemination.

In July 1998 we organized the first Institute of Physics Environmental Physics Summer School at Exeter University for school teachers and university lecturers. Apparently this was the first of its type of all the subject groups at the Institute of Physics.

In May 2000 celebration of the 10th anniversary of the Environmental Physics Group. This included a photographic exhibition with 18 frames of photographs depicting the diversity and aspects of the work of the Group and its Education Committee.

Since 1996 Nigel and Peter have been jointly editing and co-writing a textbook aimed at the "A" level/First year undergraduate interface entitled "An Introduction to Environmental Physics : Planet Earth, Life and Climate". It has been published by Taylor and Francis in Spring 2001. The chapters have been written by:

Peter Hughes	(Environmental Physics Group)
Nigel Mason	(Reader in Physics, UCL)
Randall McMullan	(GNVQ Development Office, London)
Ross Reynolds	(Lecturer in Meteorology, University of Reading)
Lester Simmonds	(Reader in Soil Physics, University of Reading)
John Twidell	(Professor of Engineering Physics, De Montfort University)

At present the Committee is preparing an **Environmental Physics Directory**. This aims to provide students and teachers with the means by which they can access information in the world of Environmental Physics. This includes useful addresses, references in books and articles in journals, ideas for practical work in Environmental Physics both in the laboratory and in the field. We will be grateful if any reader would like to submit information and/or activities for inclusion.

We are now looking forward to the challenges and excitements of the next 10 years!

P. Hughes

Committee of the EPG

Energetic and committed volunteers wanted!!

Teachers and lecturers interested in science in the Environment who are willing to make a contribution to the development of Environmental Physics in schools and colleges are welcome to join us on the Education Committee of the Institute of Physics' Environmental Physics Group.

1990-2000 : in these 10 years we were involved in bringing Environmental Physics on to the curricula of various "A" level examination boards, developed curriculum support materials and worked with groups at York University, Open University and the Institute of Physics in developing new environmental-related initiatives.

It has organized meetings and INSET for teachers in schools and lecturers in universities. It has helped to produce the textbook "An Introduction to Environmental Physics : Planet Earth, Life and Climate" aimed at "A" level and GNVQ students and first year undergraduates.

Plans for 2001-2010 : we are looking to expand our operational base, especially into the areas that border Environmental Physics such as Geology, Geography and Biology. We have been approached by a representative from a national newspaper to contribute on the Internet, materials for pupils in schools at various key stages. We see expansion into media-based Environmental Physics provision and the generation of materials for pupils in the primary and secondary sectors.

If you have enthusiasm for Science, with its linkages to Mathematics, Engineering and Technology, and would like to contribute and make a difference to what is happening in schools regarding environmental issues, please contact:

Peter Hughes
Westminster Kingsway College
Sidmouth Street
London WC1H 8JB

(Work) : 0207-306-5786
Fax : 0207-306-5800
e-mail : phughes@kingsway.ac.uk

Chair: Prof. Edward Youngs	9 Roundwood Park, Harpenden, Herts. AL5 3AB. Tel. (01582) 460859 or (01525) 863032, fax (01525) 863300, email: e.g.youngs@ukgateway.net
Vice-Chair: Dr. Alastair McCartney	Dept. of Crop and Disease Management, IACR-Rothamsted, Harpenden, Herts. AL5 2JQ. Tel. (01582) 763133 x 2246, fax (01582) 760981, email: alastair.mccartney@bbsrc.ac.uk
Honorary secretary: Dr. Peter Hodgson	BIRAL, PO Box 2, 1 Beach Road West, Portishead, Bristol BS20 7JB. Tel. (01275) 817077, fax (01275) 817277, email: p.hodgson@biral.com
Editor: Dr. Derek Rose	Dept. of Agricultural and Environmental Science, University of Newcastle upon Tyne, Newcastle upon Tyne, NE1 7RU. Tel. (0191) 222 6975, fax (0191) 222 5228, email: p.d.thoms@ncl.ac.uk
Members:	
Dr. Karen Aplin	ASRG, Dept. of Environmental Sciences, University of Hertfordshire, College Lane, Hatfield, Herts, AL10 9AB. Tel. (01707) 286143, fax (01707) 285258, email: k.l.aplin@herts.ac.uk
Dr. Ian Colbeck	Institute for Environmental Research, Dept. of Biological and Chemical Sciences, Central Campus, University of Essex, Wivehoe Park, Colchester CO4 3SQ. Tel. (01206) 872 203, fax (01206) 872592, email: colbi@essex.ac.uk
Dr. John Garland	48 Priory Orchard, Wantage, Oxon., OX12 9EL. Tel. (01235) 762361, fax (01235) 770059, email: john.garland@online.rednet.co.uk
Mr. Peter Hughes	Westminster Kingsway College, Sidmouth Street, London WC1H 8JB. Tel. (020) 7306 5786, fax (020) 7306 5800, email: phughes@kingsway.ac.uk
Ms. Sheila Morris	Dept. of Physics, University of Bristol. email: sheila.morris@bristol.ac.uk
Ms. Lucy Parkin	WS Atkins Environment, Woodcote Grove, Ashley Road, Epsom, Surrey, KT18 5BW. Tel. (01372) 756163, fax (01372) 740005, email: lkparkin@wsatkins.co.uk
Dr. Douglas Peirson	18 Nuneham Square, Abingdon, Oxon., OX14 1EH. Tel: (01235) 520454.
Ms. Alexandra Wilson	Research and Development, Ove Arup & Partners, 13 Fitzroy Street, London W1P 6BQ. Tel. (020) 7465 3045, fax (020) 7465 3669, email: alexandra.wilson@arup.com